

Design of Hardware Performance Counters Collection for Dataset Generation

Suren Harutyunyan Gevorgyan, Eduardo César, Anna Sikora¹

Abstract— The article presents an independent methodology to collect hardware performance metrics for different architectures, in order to create datasets for further use in Machine Learning models. The discussion is a step-by-step presentation of how to achieve this goal. The work presents the theoretical logic behind the methodology, while talking about the background work that has been performed recently. It also shows an empirical way of collecting hardware performance metrics, discussing the necessary tooling and hardware requirements in order to perform the experiments. These datasets will be key in the path towards being able to tune multiple parameters or the creation of architecture independent models. For that reason we need to create a dataset that is consistent, and updated.

Keywords— dynamic tuning, performance analysis, parallel applications, high performance computing, openmp

I. INTRODUCTION

Nowadays, in the High Performance Computing landscape there is a constant development of systems with the aim of satisfying the increasing computational power demand produced by complex scientific simulations and problems arising in different fields. The current solution to these problems has been the matching of the compute demand by complex systems, with more resources, *idem est*, with an ever increasing number of cores in a processor and use of systems with multiple processors.

Even though more resources are necessary, there is also a need to monitor the performance, its possible problems, and the sources of these problems. In short, there is a need to model the performance, which is the path towards finding an abstract representation of the system at hand. To create an abstract representation we need to assemble various metrics available in the system, and create parallel code regions' representations. These abstract representations can take different forms. For example code signatures characterize the behaviour of the different sections of the system, and are comprised of values, like the memory accesses at each level, the execution time, and other events.

We must also take into account that, with more hardware features, there are more metrics that can be measured, thus creating a large amount of relationships. This problem is exacerbated by the various available parallel programming paradigms with multiple modifiable options. And if there is another objective of achieving architecture independence, this

multiplicity of measurable metrics renders the task near impossible.

This triple bind of increased resources, various architectures, and parallel programming paradigms, creates an insurmountable task of modelling the performance for performance tuning by expert systems. This creates the need of dynamically producing performance models, or at least generate the tooling to aid in their creation. As we commented before, we are confronted with vast amounts of data. The main methods that make use of large amounts of data are related to Machine Learning. These, in recent years, have been able to generate an unmatched performance and accuracy on tasks where large amounts of data need to be analyzed.

During recent times great strides have been made to systematize the generation of performance models. The traditional approach of using analytical model for parameter predictions was not enough, so for that reason these were substituted by Machine Learning models in order to automatically create performance models. With the use of Machine Learning for generating performance models, the problem of the accurate prediction of parallel application parameters presents three difficulties.

First, one must correctly select a statistical model, or a proper Artificial Neural Network architecture. Second, a careful selection of the metrics to be used to characterize the behaviour of a parallel code region must be warranted. Third, in order to achieve architecture independence, for each architecture that is targeted, there is the task of building a representative and balanced dataset of patterns found in parallel applications. Some of these problems were tackled in recent works by Alcaraz [1] [2] [3], where a systematic approach was presented to achieve the objectives of finding a proper set of metrics in a system, building representative datasets for performance tuning, and managing naturally imbalanced datasets. The final objective was to answer if Machine Learning can be used to modify and recommend tunable parameters in the OpenMP paradigm.

Alas, the experiments of these works were performed using non homogeneous datasets, e.g., the generated datasets, diverged in the problem sizes, or used similar data sizes, but different code kernels. Since the objective is to use Machine Learning methods this lack of homogeneity can pose challenges, especially during experiment reproducibility.

Another point is that these datasets were focused on Intel systems, which poses the question of method independence.

Consequently, if we want to continue advancing

¹Dpt. of Computer Architecture and Operating Systems, School of Engineering, Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona, e-mail: suren.harutyunyan@uab.cat, eduardo.cesar@uab.cat, anna.sikora@uab.cat.

in challenges, like the tuning of multiple parameters, the creation of architecture independent models, etc., we need to create a dataset that is consistent, updated, harmonized, and complete.

For that reason, and in order to achieve these objectives, here we present a methodology of performance counter data collection in different architectures.

This document is structured as follows. Section 2 presents the previous work that has been performed in this field, and the results that were achieved applying Machine Learning using these types of datasets. Section 3 shows the background research and methods on which this work is based. Section 4 focuses on the system of the collection of hardware metrics and the creation of hardware counter datasets. Section 5 shows the practical results of following the methodology on 2 different systems, discussing pre-set events, problem sizes, and code kernels. Finally, Section 6 provides a brief summary of the presented effort.

II. RELATED WORK

In this section we will describe the main related works that have recently appeared in the literature. These are projects that have attempted using Machine Learning techniques for parallel application tuning and analysis. The goal is similar to the described above, in that, the models are used to analyze the performance, and improve it by modifying tuning the application's parameters.

Having said that, we must mention that these works are not using a systematic approach of curating a dataset, neither follow a process of determining the quality of the same dataset.

First, we will mention READEX (Runtime Exploitation of Application Dynamism for Energy-efficient eXascale computing) [4] [5]. It is a European project with the objective of creating dynamic auto-tuning tools to improve performance and energy efficiency in exascale computing for heterogeneous and embedded systems. A second objective of the project was the application of Machine Learning to adapt the parameters according to the dynamic behaviour in HPC applications.

The technique READEX uses is the following. First, it uses the Periscope Tuning Framework [6] and a *representative* dataset to perform a previous analysis, with the objective of discovering important regions, characterizing dynamism and obtain estimates about performance and energy efficiency of the application that will be executed later.

The, READEX [7] used Artificial Neural Networks, Support Vector Machines, and Decision Trees to predict optimal hardware parameters, namely the number of threads, and core and uncore frequency, in order to consume energy more efficiently. The best model was the Artificial Neural Network that was trained on four sparse matrix algorithms.

Another project is APARF (automatic, portable and adaptive runtime feedback-driven framework).

It is framework that selects the optimal task scheduling for a particular application, using a combination of low-level tasking runtime APIs, profiling and Machine Learning [8].

To train the model the authors use various task-based applications from *Barcelona OpenMP Tasks Suite* [9]. The idea behind this, is that these show different behaviours and task characteristics, which lead the authors to consider these as a balanced and a representative set. Each of the applications from the suite is executed using different problem sizes, number of threads, compiler flags, and task scheduling configurations. To manage task scheduling the authors take into account the data locality, and load balancing. To describe the former, the authors use hardware performance events which are related to cache accesses and misses, a ratio between the the cycles and the instructions, and the TLB misses. Consecutively, the latter, is represented by the the timings in each application's thread.

Once these tasks were performed, the authors created an Artificial Neural Network, in order to classify the program between different cases, namely a simple case, a public case, and a default case. These cases are related to different task pool configurations. The results that were obtained from the classifier were then compared against the default task scheduling configurations of various compilers, achieving an average accuracy of 93 %, and a performance enhancement of 25 % over the default configurations.

We must also mention the BLISS project [10] which uses Bayesian Optimization techniques to build models, while the application is still executing. The idea behind this approach is to avoid offline training. This method, tries to modify multiple tunable parameters in the application, but it does not try to find an optimal configuration with a search algorithm. Instead, it uses the parameters for each of the configurations, and a given output metric (e.g., execution time) which will help in building a performance model with Bayesian Optimization.

Once the probabilistic model is obtained, it can be used during the parameter search as a guide, and the model will be able to make suggestions regarding the application's parameters in order to optimize the objective function, thus improving the performance of the application. This Bayesian Optimization approach found the quasi optimal parameter configurations.

The next work is the Piecewise Holistic Autotuning with CERE project. It is a proposal that would help automatically tune OpenMP applications with the CERE tool [11]. The functionality of CERE is the decomposition of applications into little code regions, that it calls codelets, which are in turn then mapped to OpenMP parallel regions.

The project, *per se*, classifies these codelets into clusters, with the aim to find the codelets that have similar performance signatures. The performance signatures generated by CERE are a combination of static metrics (related to code characteristics), and dy-

dynamic metrics (hardware performance counters, and memory bandwidth).

The results of the project obtained using the NAS benchmark with an accuracy of 93.66 %, and a 6,55× reduction of the time that is required to evaluate each of the codelets.

Another interesting recent work is the Kernel Tuning Toolkit [12] in the space of GPUs and application code optimization. The main problem tackled in this case is that of searching the tuning space of performance relevant source code parameters. The main problem is that the search in the tuning space will produce overhead if we have a big tuning space, and/or when the tuning process has to be repeated too many times due to changes in the data or hardware. The paper introduces a method for searching tuning spaces, using hardware performance counters, which later are used to navigate the search process towards faster implementations. Mainly, since it builds models that are problem specific, these can be used during auto-tuning on unseen inputs or GPUs.

The model reduces the number of tests that have to be performed during auto-tuning, and shows a superior real-time convergence result compared to random searchers, or the state-of-the-art optimisation-based Basin hopping searcher implemented in Kernel Tuner.

III. BACKGROUND

In this section we will first focus on the background work that was performed in order to achieve the system of hardware counter collection and further developments that drove this effort.

As we mentioned in the introductory section the body of work on which this paper is based was presented by Alcaraz in a series of papers [1], [2] [3], which culminated in the [13]. In the the latter study Alcaraz introduced a proper method of collecting hardware counter data, with the focus multi-thread applications using OpenMP. The idea was to build a representative dataset that would help explore the question if it was possible to use Machine Learning methods in order to generate models for use in performance tuning of parallel applications.

It must be noted that a simple collection of hardware metrics is not sufficient in order to achieve an effective use of Machine Learning techniques. There was a need use a systematic method to determine the feature set that characterizes shared memory parallel regions, and also generates representative and balanced datasets. The work body and the solution to these challenges was divided in 3 parts.

A. Determining the Features

First, in [1] the authors introduced a methodology to find the proper set of metrics for characterizing the behaviour of an OpenMP parallel code region. This allowed to drastically reduce the number of metrics necessary to correctly characterize a code region, plus it reduced the metric measurement overhead. It made possible to use less than the 50 % of the available

general purpose counters, but without loss of information.

This was performed by selecting a set of parallel code regions, and performing a redundancy analysis based on PCA and the Pearson Correlation Coefficient of the performance counters' values collected for these regions. The collection of the values of hardware performance counters for the parallel regions of an application was achieved by the integration of PAPI [14] into MATE [15].

It should be noted that the dataset for this work was obtained using 4 kernels (namely the Copy, Scale, Add, and Triad functions) from the STREAM [16] benchmark. This reduced set can pose generalization problems, and it informs us of the need to rebuild the dataset.

B. Creating the Dataset

Second, there still remained the task of building datasets/pattern collections that are representative of the most common OpenMP parallel regions, and are balanced, avoiding the over/under-representation of these regions in the dataset. This will be key during the training phase of the performance models.

In this case, to establish if a parallel region is represented in the dataset the steps are the following. First, for a particular parallel region multiple executions are performed, varying their number of threads and their binding. During these executions a set of hardware counter metrics are logged, which will aid in constructing a signature for this parallel region.

This signature would next be correlated with the rest of the signatures in the dataset. If the correlation degree is high, it is assumed that the parallel region is already represented in the dataset, and it can be safely discarded. On the contrary, if the correlation is low it is included in the greater dataset generating the necessary signatures.

This method was proposed as a solution to solving the problem of building representative and balanced datasets, and was presented in the following work by Alcaraz et al. [2].

Related to the issue presented above, this work was using a dataset that was built using the PolyBench [17] [18] benchmark. The issue was exacerbated by using different problem sizes and an old system architecture.

C. Creating Tuning Models

Third, and finally, there was a proposal of how to generate models for performance tuning using the previous methodology of pattern collection creation. This part's aim is to solve pattern collection balancing issues that are due to characteristics of the hardware and/or the parallel programming paradigm, which would in turn improve the accuracy of the Machine Learning methods that were analysed in the study, namely (K Nearest Neighbours, Decision Trees and Artificial Neural Networks).

In the study, the author built the previously mentioned base models, to predict the number of threads,

since these provided better accuracy than other Machine Learning algorithms. The proposal was presented in the paper by Alcaraz et al. [3].

For the issues presented above, and the use of Machine Learning, the creation of a harmonized and complete dataset is a paramount objective.

IV. METHODOLOGY FOR HARDWARE COUNTER COLLECTION

After the previous overview, we will focus primarily on the first challenge mentioned above. Here we will present the methodology of selecting hardware performance metrics that will be used as features to characterize the executions of parallel OpenMP regions. We must keep in mind that the system must be usable for a variety of architectures, since the goal is to produce Machine Learning models that will be independent of hardware architectures. Having said that let's delve into the task at hand.

A. Preset Events and Compatibilities

Alcaraz et al. [1] presented a system of obtaining these metrics primarily using PAPI (Performance Application Programming Interface) [14]. The tool provides a consistent interface and methodology for use of the performance counter hardware found in most major microprocessors. PAPI enables the observation in near real time of the relation between software performance and processor events.

Since we will be working with different architectures, there is a high chance that the measurable counters that are available for each one may be different. It is for that reason, and in order to generalize our method, we will be working with the preset events for each system, and not the native events. This method, may sacrifice the number of events that will be available, but on the other hand it gains in generalization capabilities.

After obtaining the list of events for each architecture, we must determine the correct compatible groups for the events, which increases the measuring precision. To clarify the previous statement we must add that there is a limitation in the number of registers in processors to read hardware performance counters at the same time [13].

Additionally, there are incompatibilities when accessing hardware performance counters, so some counters cannot be read at the same time as others. Because of this limitation, groups are created and compatible events are measured simultaneously in time intervals using multiplexing. If the number of events to measure is reduced, each group has more measuring time, increasing their precision [13].

B. Problem Sizes

Once the hardware counters are obtained and assembled into compatible groups, we must think of the problem sizes, and the problems that will be measured.

Obtaining problem sizes is critical for purposes of stressing the different memory levels that will be

available in each architecture. Consequently the calculation of the problem sizes must be proportional to the memory size in each level of the memory hierarchy. That means we are presented with two computations.

1. **Inside Processor Memory:** For the memory levels that are inside the processor, meaning L1, L2, L3 caches, must have problem sizes that are proportional to the number of the physical cores in one processor. These are the following:

a) **Private Cache Levels:** Usually each core in the processor has a private memory that can be used by the threads allocated in that core. These are the L1 and L2 caches.

For our purposes, we will need to stress the private cache levels, for which we will create multiple problem sizes, which will be directly proportional to the resources. These will be defined by the multiplication of the number of private cache levels and the number of cores in a processor.

So for each cache level, the problem size is constructed such that it starts with the size of one private cache and is consequently multiplied by the different core numbers. This process continues until reaching the accumulated size of the private caches in the same level.

b) **Shared Cache Levels:** The processors also share memory between all the cores. Usually there is a shared L3 cache. In order to be able to stress the shared cache levels we have to start with a problem size that is bigger than the accumulated size of the lower level caches. We will keep increasing the problem size until reaching just under the maximum shared memory in the cache level. The logic behind this is that, in no case the lower cache levels will be able to lend the necessary memory, and the higher level in the hierarchy will not be accessed.

2. **Outside Processor Memory:** For the memory levels that are outside the processor, the problem size must be proportional to the number of processors in the system, and not the number of physical cores. The problem sizes are defined in the following way:

a) **Main Memory:** Clearly the largest problem sizes are intended for the main memory, and these are proportional to the number of processors available plus 1. Following this logic, the first problem size will be bigger than the last cache level of the processor. The rest of the problem sizes are obtained by gradually increasing the memory requirements, effectively doubling the size each time. The final size is 1.5 times the total size of the last level cache of all the the processors.

C. Kernels and OpenMP Parameters

After defining the problem sizes, we will briefly discuss the kernels that will be using during the the

experimentation, and the OpenMP parameters that will be used to modify the behaviour of the execution.

First of all we will talk about the candidate kernels for building the dataset. The backbone of the experimentation is based on 2 benchmarks, namely STREAM [16] and PolyBench [17] [18]. The following is a brief description of the benchmarks:

1. **STREAM:** Sustainable Memory Bandwidth in High Performance Computers [16] is a synthetic benchmark that measures sustainable memory bandwidth (in MB/s) and the corresponding computation rate for simple vector kernels. It is composed of simple vector kernels to measure sustainable memory bandwidth [13].
2. **PolyBench:** This program is a collection of benchmarks with multiple kernels [17] [18]. In our case the version 4 of the program was used which includes 23 different benchmarks divided in different categories (datamining, linear algebra, medley, and stencils) [13].

From these, we selected the code kernels on which the experimentation will be performed. Again, with the aim of homogenizing the dataset creation process, these kernels will be applied to both systems. The details surrounding the kernels will be discussed in the following section.

Also, we would like to have a discussion on the OpenMP parameters that will be modified for the different executions. These will be modified, because these parameters will be used during syntonization phase. These will be the following:

1. **Number of Threads:** The first parameter to be modified is the number of the threads. The executions start with 1 thread, and this parameter keeps increasing by 1 after each execution, with the an upper limit of the threads available in the system.
2. **Thread Affinity Policy:** The executions of the kernels will be performed first with a *close* thread affinity policy, and next with a *spread* affinity. To ensure this, it is important to correctly set the OMP_PLACES and the OMP_PROC_BIND environment variables. The former represents the smallest unit of execution exposed by the execution environment, typically a hardware thread. The latter's value set the thread affinity policy to be used for parallel regions at the corresponding nested level.
3. **Scheduling Policy:** The executions of the kernels will also modify the scheduling policy, which distributes the loop iterations to the threads. The parameters involve cycling through the *static*, *dynamic*, and *guided* runtimes. These will also be dependent on the following parameter which is the chunk size.
4. **Chunk Size:** Associated to the previous parameter, the chunk sizes that will be used during the executions are the following three. The first is the *default* chunk size of 1. The next chunk

sizes will be computed according to:

$$\frac{1\%ofIterations}{NumberOfThreads} \quad (1)$$

and,

$$\frac{10\%ofIterations}{NumberOfThreads} \quad (2)$$

After the above parameters are set, we must perform the executions. It must be done in the following manner. We must execute the code kernels for each group of events, for each thread available in the system, for each size, and for each chosen tunable OpenMP parameter in this order. The OpenMP parameters will consist of the following ones:

1. **Thread Affinity**
2. **Scheduling Type**
3. **Chunk Size**

In order to achieve statistical significance and build a dataset for a particular parallel region, we will perform multiple executions for each case. During these executions a pre selected group of hardware counter metrics will be logged, which will aid in constructing a signature for this parallel region.

In summary, the number of executions can be calculated according to the following formula:

$$E = S \times T \times P \times OP \times N \quad (3)$$

where E is the number of executions, S is the number of counter sets, T is the number of threads, P is the number of problem sizes, OP is the number of OpenMP parameter combinations, and N is the number of repetitions.

V. CONCRETE DATASET CREATION

Once we know the methodology, we can present concrete results of the above section. Since our goal is to build datasets that are consistent, updated, harmonized, and complete, our starting point will be the systems on which we will perform the experiments.

A. Hardware Architecture

We will start with the architecture details. As we mentioned above, we will use two different systems. The first system is an Intel processor, the second is an AMD one.

1. **Intel system:** It is a Xeon E5-4620 composed of 4 sockets, with 8 cores per socket, and 2 threads per core. Its memory hierarchy is composed by a 32KB L1 data cache and a 256KB L2 for each core, and a shared 16MB L3 cache in each processor. The total amount of main memory is 126GB.
2. **AMD system:** It is an EPYC 7551 composed of 2 sockets, 4 NUMA nodes per socket, with 32 cores per sockets, and 2 threads per core. Its memory hierarchy is composed by a 32KB L1 data cache and a 512KB L2 for each core, and

a shared 16MB L3 cache in each NUMA node. The total amount of main memory is 251GB.

The summary for the 2 architectures is shown in Table I.

Table I: Hardware architecture details.

Arch./System	Xeon E5-4620	EPYC 7551
Sockets	4	2
Cores/Socket	8	32
Threads/Core	2	2
L1 Cache	32KB	32KB
L2 Cache	256KB	512KB
L3 Cache	16MB	16MB
Main Mem.	126GB	251GB

The memory hierarchy of the systems was obtained with the The Portable Hardware Locality (`hwloc`) [19] software package, which provides a portable abstraction (across OS, versions, architectures, etc.) of the hierarchical topology of the architectures.

A second tool used to examine the thread, cache and NUMA topology was *LIKWID* [20]. We obtained the information executing the command *likwid-topology*. In general, *LIKWID* is a tool suite of command line applications and a library for performance oriented programs. The tool can be used in a wide range of processors and architectures from different vendors.

B. Preset Events per System

After having introduced the systems that will be used in our experimentation, we can talk about the hardware performance counters data collection. We first will have to execute the command *papi-avail -a* to obtain the available PAPI preset and user defined events.

In the case of Xeon E5-4620, PAPI reports 50 preset events available in the processor. On the other hand, for the EPYC 7551, PAPI reports 24 preset events available in the processor. This difference in the number of preset events between the Intel machine and the AMD one, is most likely due to the lack of support for AMD.

After obtaining the list for both machines, we have classified the measurable events for the processors in the types as shown in Table II

Table II: Events by type in the 2 experimented processors.

Type/System	Xeon E5-4620	EPYC 7551
Branches	6	2
L1 cache	5	6
L2 cache	14	1
L3 cache	9	0
TLB	2	2
Cycles	3	2
Operations	3	3
Instructions	8	8
Total	50	24

The classification is straightforward. The Branches category refers to the conditional branch instructions. The L1, L2 and L3 cache categories, refer to Level 1, 2, and 3 data or instruction cache accesses, read, hits, misses, etc.

The TLB preset events, refer to data or instruction translation lookaside buffer misses. The Cycles category is a broad one, referring from cycles with no instruction issue to total cycles. The Operations and Instructions categories refer to the events measuring floating point operations and instructions.

Once this step is finished, we can determine the correct compatible groups for the events. This step has to be performed for each architecture, and it is a combination of an automatic and a manual process.

This step is done with the command *papi-event-chooser PRESET [EVENT]*, that reports which events are compatible with an event or a list of events, with the same output format as *papi-avail* [14]. In the case of selecting incompatible events, the following error is printed: *Event [EVENT] can't be counted with others -1* [14].

Our results show 12 different groups for the E5-4620 (Intel) system, and 4 groups for the EPYC 7551 (AMD) system.

C. Problem Size Results

After determining the correct groups for each of the architectures, we have to determine the problem sizes following the systems presented in the previous section.

C.1 Xeon E5-4620 Sizes

For the Xeon E5-4620 system we used the following formulas to perform the calculations.

The problem sizes to stress the L1 Cache were computed with this formula:

$$L_{1n} = 31KiB \times n, \quad (4)$$

where n is

$$1 \leq n \leq 8.$$

The n denotes the number of iterations per memory level. This will yield a minimum size of 32KiB, and maximum size of 256KiB.

For the problem sizes to stress the L2 Cache, we have used this equation:

$$L_{2n} = 255KiB \times n, \quad (5)$$

where n is

$$1 \leq n \leq 8.$$

The range of the L2 problem sizes is a minimum size of 256KiB, and a maximum size of 2MiB, just under the L3 limit.

The problem sizes to stress the L3 Cache were computed using these three formulas, depending on the number of iterations, in order to reach the upper limit, we aimed to use:

$$L_{3n} = \begin{cases} 1024KiB \times n + 512KiB & \text{where } 2 \leq n \leq 4 \\ 1024KiB \times n & \text{where } 5 \leq n \leq 7 \\ 1024KiB \times n - 256KiB & \text{where } n = 8 \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

In the case of L3, the minimum size starts with 2.5MiB, which is over the cumulative size of the previous levels. The maximum size is 15.5MiB.

Finally, for the main memory, the size was computed as followed:

$$M_n = \begin{cases} 1024KiB \times 16,5 \times n & \text{where } 1 \leq n \leq 4 \\ (\sum_{n=1}^n M_n) \times 1,5 & \text{where } n = n - 1 \end{cases} \quad (7)$$

These calculations yield us a minimum problem size of 16.5MiB for the Main Memory, and maximum size of 74.25MiB.

C.2 EPYC 7551 Sizes

For the EPYC 7551 system we used the following formulas to perform the calculations. Note that the formulations slightly differ from their previous counterparts.

The problem sizes to stress the L1 Cache were computed with this formula:

$$L_{1n} = 31KiB \times n, \quad (8)$$

where n is

$$1 \leq n \leq 33.$$

This will yield a minimum size of 32KiB, and maximum size of 1024KiB.

For the problem sizes to stress the L2 Cache, we have used this equation:

$$L_{2n} = 1024KiB + 511KiB \times n, \quad (9)$$

where n is

$$1 \leq n \leq 30.$$

The range of the L2 problem sizes is a minimum size of 1571KiB, and a maximum size of 15.8MiB, just under the L3 limit.

The problem sizes to stress the L3 Cache were computed using this formula:

$$L_{3n} = 1024KiB \times 17 + 512KiB + 4096KiB \times n, \quad (10)$$

where n is

$$0 < n \leq 11.$$

In the case of L3, the minimum size starts with 18MiB, which is over the cumulative size of the previous levels. The maximum size is 65MiB.

Finally, for the main memory, the size was computed as followed:

$$M_n = \begin{cases} 8192KiB \times 16 \times n & \text{where } 1 \leq n < 3 \\ (\sum_{n=1}^n M_n) \times 1,5 & \text{where } n = n - 1 \end{cases} \quad (11)$$

These calculations yield us a minimum problem size of 131MiB for the Main Memory, and maximum size of 589.5MiB.

The summary of the results can be seen in Table III:

Table III: Problem sizes by memory level and system type.

Sizes/System	Xeon E5-4620	EPYC 7551
L1 Cache	32 - 256KiB	32 - 1024KiB
L2 Cache	256 - 2048KiB	1571 - 15872KiB
L3 Cache	2.5 - 15.5MiB	18 - 65MiB
Main Mem.	16.5 - 74.25MiB	131 - 589.5MiB

Note that, since we will be using 4 byte integers, a division by 4 will be necessary in order to obtain the experimental problem sizes.

D. Experimentation Kernels

Next, we will present the benchmarks that will be used during the experimentation phase. The backbone of the experimentation is based on the 16 kernels that were extracted from the STREAM [16] and PolyBench [17] [18] benchmarks. From the former we used primarily 4 kernels, and the remaining 12 were provided by the latter.

To these kernels we have also added 2 new code sections which are the classic Collatz problem, and a Friendly number extractor program. The aim for these additions is to include programs which are computationally intensive, with load balancing problems, and with few memory access operations. These code kernels are introduced in the experimentation phase specifically to target the OpenMP scheduling and chunk size parameters, that were mentioned in the previous section.

Finally, once we have the architecture details, and after computing the counter groups, the number of threads, and the problem sizes, and OpenMP parameters, we have to decide the number of executions. To achieve statistical significance each code kernel will be executed 100 times. A summary of this data point can be observed in the Table IV.

Table IV: Execution parameter summary.

Execs./System	Xeon E5-4620	EPYC 7551
Counter Sets	12	6
Threads	32	64
Problem Sizes	29	78
OpenMP Pars.	11	11
Reps.	100	100
Total	12249600	21964800

VI. CONCLUSIONS

In this work we have summarized the background work developed by Alcaraz [13] and the motivation behind creating datasets for the purposes of using Machine Learning models in order to tune performance parameters of OpenMP applications. These works were performed with a single architecture and the analysis was performed using different datasets with different features.

For those reasons, and with the aim of creating a consistent, updated, and homogeneous datasets, here we presented a methodology of collecting hardware performance metrics, and creating these datasets.

The aim is that the presented system will be nearly universal across architectures, and will allow the creation of a homogeneous dataset that will help during experiment reproduction.

In our case we presented the application of the collection system, for two machines from different vendors. Intel and AMD, in this case. We presented how to examine their memory hierarchies, and how, using the PAPI tool [14], to obtain the counters available in the system. We followed this by showing how and why to group these counters in different measurement groups. We also noted, that these preset events, may differ across systems.

Next, we discussed how to compute the problem sizes, in order to stress the various levels of memory during our metric collection. These results were presented for each system and for each memory level, ranging from the L1 cache to the main memory level. Following the problem sizes we discussed which problems would serve as the code kernels during the executions, and presented main benchmarks for this purpose, and 2 additional problems.

Finally, we showed the different OpenMP tunable parameters that will be used during the executions of these kernels in order to observe the behaviour of the kernels under various circumstances.

Overall, we presented a guided process through which to collect hardware metrics with the aim of hardware counter dataset creation. We believe that following this methodical approach will guarantee the creation of a robust dataset that will yield solid results during the future analysis and experimentation phase of the study.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This work has been granted by the Ministerio de Ciencia e Innovación MCIN AEI/10.13039/501100011033 under contract PID2020-113614RB-C21 and by the Generalitat de Catalunya GenCat-DIUe (GRC) project 2017-SGR-313.

REFERENCES

- [1] Jordi Alcaraz, Anna Sikora, and Eduardo César, “Hardware counters’ space reduction for code region characterization,” pp. 74–86, 2019.
- [2] Jordi Alcaraz, Steven Sleder, Ali Tehrani Jamsaz, Anna Sikora, Ali Jannesari, Joan Sorribes, and Eduardo César, “Building representative and balanced datasets of openmp parallel regions,” pp. 67–74, 2021.
- [3] Jordi Alcaraz, Ali Tehrani Jamsaz, Akash Dutta, Anna Sikora, Ali Jannesari, Joan Sorribes, and Eduardo César, “Predicting number of threads using balanced datasets for openmp regions.,” 2022.
- [4] Per Gunnar Kjeldsberg, Andreas Gocht, Michael Gerndt, Lubomir Riha, Joseph Schuchart, and Umbreen Sabir Mian, “Readex: Linking two ends of the computing continuum to improve energy-efficiency in dynamic applications,” in *Design, Automation Test in Europe Conference Exhibition (DATE), 2017*, 2017, pp. 109–114.
- [5] Joseph Schuchart, Michael Gerndt, Per Kjeldsberg, Michael Lysaght, David Horák, Lubomír Řiha, Andreas Gocht, Mohammed Sourouri, Madhura Kumaraswamy, Anamika Chowdhury, Magnus Jahre, Kai Diethelm, Othman Bouizi, Umbreen Mian, Jakub Kružík, Radim Sojka, Martin Beseda, Venkatesh Kannan, Zakaria Bendifallah, and Wolfgang Nagel, “The readex formalism for automatic tuning for energy efficiency,” *Computing*, vol. 99, 08 2017.
- [6] “Automatic tuning of hpc applications - the periscope tuning framework (ptf),” in *Automatic Tuning of HPC Applications - The Periscope Tuning Framework (PTF)*, Michael Gerndt, E. Cesar, and Siegfried Benkner, Eds. Shaker Verlag, 2015.
- [7] Vojtech Nikl, Ondrej Vsocky, Lubomír Řiha, and Jan Zapletal, “Optimal hardware parameters prediction for best energy-to-solution of sparse matrix operations using machine learning techniques,” 07 2018.
- [8] Ahmad Qawasmeh, Abid M. Malik, and Barbara M. Chapman, “Adaptive openmp task scheduling using runtime apis and machine learning,” in *2015 IEEE 14th International Conference on Machine Learning and Applications (ICMLA)*, 2015, pp. 889–895.
- [9] Alejandro Duran, Xavier Teruel, Roger Ferrer, Xavier Martorell, and Eduard Ayguade, “Barcelona openmp tasks suite: A set of benchmarks targeting the exploitation of task parallelism in openmp,” in *2009 International Conference on Parallel Processing*, 2009, pp. 124–131.
- [10] Rohan Roy, Tirthak Patel, Vijay Gadepally, and Devesh Tiwari, “Bliss: auto-tuning complex applications using a pool of diverse lightweight learning models,” 06 2021, pp. 1280–1295.
- [11] Mihail Popov, Chadi Akel, Yohan Chatelain, William Jalby, and Pablo de Oliveira Castro, “Piecewise holistic autotuning of parallel programs with cere,” *Concurrency and Computation: Practice and Experience*, vol. 29, 06 2017.
- [12] Jiří Filipovič, Jana Hozzová, Amin Nezarat, Jaroslav Olha, and Filip Petrovič, “Using hardware performance counters to speed up autotuning convergence on gpus,” 2021.
- [13] Jordi Alcaraz, *Towards Automatic Generation of Performance Models for Dynamic Tuning using Machine Learning*, PhD dissertation, Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona, 2021.
- [14] K. London, S. Moore, P. Mucci, K. Seymour, and R. Luczak, “The papi cross-platform interface to hardware performance counters,” June 2021.
- [15] A. Morajko O. Morajko T. Margalef and E. Luque, “Mate: Dynamic performance tuning environment.,” p. 98–107, 2004.
- [16] John McCalpin, “Memory bandwidth and machine balance in high performance computers,” *IEEE Technical Committee on Computer Architecture Newsletter*, pp. 19–25, 12 1995.
- [17] Tomofumi Yuki, “Understanding polybench/c 3.2 kernels,” 2014.
- [18] T. Yuki and L.-N. Pouchet, “Polybench 4.0,” 2015.
- [19] François Broquedis, Jérôme Clet-Ortega, Stéphanie Moreaud, Nathalie Furmento, Brice Goglin, Guillaume Mercier, Samuel Thibault, and Raymond Namyst, “hwloc: a Generic Framework for Managing Hardware Affinities in HPC Applications,” in *PDP 2010 - The 18th Euro-micro International Conference on Parallel, Distributed and Network-Based Computing*, IEEE, Ed., Pisa, Italy, Feb. 2010.
- [20] J. Treibig, G. Hager, and G. Wellein, “Likwid: A lightweight performance-oriented tool suite for x86 multicore environments,” in *Proceedings of PSTI2010, the First International Workshop on Parallel Software Tools and Tool Infrastructures*, San Diego CA, 2010.